

SIMULATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF IMPROVED INCREMENTAL CONDUCTANCE MPPT USING SEPIC CONVERTER FOR SMALL-SCALE PV SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Photovoltaic (PV) systems are widely used in the different sectors of industry. However, they have relatively low efficiency due to their dependence on temperature and solar irradiation fluctuations. Several maximum power point trackers (MPPT) have been developed in the aim of improving the efficiency of these PV systems. In this paper, an improved incremental conductance (IncCon) MPPT control technique is proposed to detect the MPP provided by a small PV system that is able to overcome the limitations of conventional algorithms such as perturb and observe (P&O) and conventional (InCon) particularly in sudden variation of solar irradiation. To this end, we started by the development and verification of a model for the PV panels in ISIS Proteus software, where the different characteristics curves I-V and P-V are plotted and compared to theoretical ones. Then, the single ended primary inductor converter (SEPIC) part and that of the MPPT controllers are presented. Finally, a simulation in a semi-virtual environment is carried out by programming the MPPT control strategies (P&O, conventional and modified IncCon) in an Arduino allowing the control of a PV system equipped with a SEPIC converter. The obtained results, showing the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, are presented and discussed.

Keywords: Photovoltaic System; MPPT; Perturb and Observe; Incremental Conductance; SEPIC Converter.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, the greenhouse effect has emerged as an environmental concern. This is due, to the escalating temperatures and the subsequent rise in weather occurrences. As part of the engaged efforts to tackle climate changes there has been a growing focus on renewable energy sources like photovoltaic (PV) systems [1]. However, their dependance on the daylight is a limitation that can be addressed by integrating energy storage devices to extend the system's autonomy.

Additionally, these PV systems face limitations in terms of efficiency due to factors such as shading and fluctuations, in temperature and solar irradiation. To tackle this challenge, researchers have developed Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) techniques that

optimize the output power of PV systems. DC-DC converters are commonly used in MPPT systems to increase the efficiency of the power transfer process [2][3] .

There is no single classification for MPPT algorithms. However, as an initial categorization, they can be classified into techniques used for uniform solar irradiation conditions (USICs) and those used for the systems facing partial shading conditions (PSCs) [4]. Furthermore, several criteria can be considered when classifying MPPT algorithms. The most significant ones are: implementation method (software or hardware), required sensors, accuracy, convergence and tracking speed, complexity and cost. Based on tracking methods, MPPTs algorithms can be classified as classical (conventional) techniques, Intelligent MPPT control techniques, optimization techniques and hybrid techniques [2], [4], [5], [6], [7].

Among the mentioned algorithms, Incremental conductance (IncCon) and perturb and observe (P&O) are widely used in practical applications. They use the power versus the voltage (P-V) curve and adjust the duty cycle of the DC-DC converter to guarantee that the working point remains at the MPP. Both algorithms have the advantage of being well-suited for the most of PV systems with a quite well performance under the most working conditions [8], [9].

For their implementation, most of the low-cost digital controllers can perform the procedure. However, these techniques suffer from steady state oscillation problem that leads to power losses in the system. P&O algorithm is continuously perturbing the P-V curves in both directions (left and right) to maintain the MPP. For the IncCon technique the MPPT is considered reached when the slope of the P-V curve equals zero. However, when using digital controller to implement the MPP algorithm, the zero value for the slope is hardly obtained due to the truncation errors in digital processing. Another drawback of these two algorithms is the inaccurate response when the solar irradiation is suddenly changed [8], [10], [11].

Different DC-DC converters are used as an intermediate interface between the PV module and the load, with the aim of maximizing the extractible power from the PV [12]. The voltage of the PV module and the load voltage are two factors that affect the converter topology selection. For example, the buck topology is only used in situations where the voltage of the PV module usually exceeds the load. In the same way, when the PV module voltage regularly drops below the load voltage, the boost topology becomes appropriate. Both choices are undoubtedly extremes considering the significant fluctuations in insolation throughout the day. But the buck-boost converter's inverted output is a drawback that makes sensing and feedback circuitry more complicated. Furthermore, the converter presents discontinuous input current, which places constraints on its overall functionality [5], [13]. A comprehensive investigation of various buck-boost converters from a range of viewpoints is provided in [8][14]. The SEPIC converter has significant advantages, such as non-inverting polarity, continuous input current, adaptability as a buck-boost converter throughout a large range, and minimal input current-ripple, despite its drawbacks, which include lower efficiency and higher cost. It is interesting that it operates well in situations that involve voltage or current [15]. Copper losses in the

inductor windings, switching losses in the MOSFET and diode, and inductor core losses are the main sources of losses in DC–DC converters. A comparative analysis of converter losses shows that switching losses are identical across all converters because they have the same number of switches (MOSFET and diode). Despite using two inductors, the SEPIC converter stands out for having lower inductor losses, which are attributable to less input current ripple and a resulting decrease in peak inductor current. The SEPIC converter is being promoted as an attractive choice for photovoltaic (PV) applications because to these special characteristics [16] .

From another point of view, it is critical to expedite the system verification process in addition to ensuring that total expenses are kept to a minimum. A number of methods have been presented, including intermediate semi-virtual verification techniques, and ranging from pure simulation to experimental verification [17], [18]. The goal of the paper is to design and develop low-cost Arduino-based modified MPPT IncCon technique for PV systems in semi virtual environment using Isis Proteus software. To achieve this goal, we began by developing and verifying a model for the PV panels in ISIS Proteus software. Next, we implemented the SEPIC converter and the MPPT controller components. Finally, we conducted a simulation in a semi-virtual environment by programming the MPPT control strategies (P&O, conventional and modified IncCon) in an Arduino. The obtained results are presented and discussed.

2. SYSTEM MODELING

2.1 PV system modeling

The behavior of solar cells has been described in the literature using a variety of models namely single and Improved single diode model (SDM and ISDM), double and modified diode model (DDM and MDDM), triple diode model (TDM) [19] . SDM is used in this paper. This model incorporates a series resistance, a current source, and a diode placed in parallel to simulate losses resulting from joule heating, as shown in Fig. 1.

Notably, this model introduces an extra shunt resistance R_{sh} . This resistance, which is typically much higher than R_s , indicates a leakage current between the upper grid and the rear contact. Its existence significantly affects the current that the model produces, nearly matching the properties of an actual cell.

Figure 1: Equivalent electric circuit of SDM for PV cells

The solar cell output current is given by equation (1)

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Where I_D presents the diode current that is given by Shockley's diode equation given by equation (2).

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{nKT}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

The PV module is constructed by assembling multiple PV cells in series and in parallel. Thus, the equation the PV module current can be expressed by equation (3).

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{k \frac{(V+IR_s)}{nV_t N_s}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

Where I_{ph} is the Photovoltaic current; I_0 is the Saturation current of the diode; N is Ideality factor; R_s is the series resistance; $V_t = \frac{KT}{q}$ is the thermal voltage; R_{sh} is the shunt resistance; N_s is number of cells in the module.

2.2 PV module characteristics.

The PV module can be described using two main curves presenting either the current or the power as a function of the PV voltage. Figure 2 shows current versus voltage curve (I-V curve) and power versus voltage curve (P-V curve) of the PV module along with the load line and the working point MPP.

Figure 2: P-V and I-V curves

2.3 PV module using ISIS Proteus software.

The used model is based on SDM. Based on the equivalent circuit of a real solar cell, the latter is presented under Proteus software as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: PV panel model using Proteus software

To verify the validity of the developed model, power and current versus voltage of the module MSX 60 PV are plotted in standard test conditions (STC) as shown in Figure.4 (a) and Figure. 4(b).

Figure 4(a): I-V characteristic of MSX 60 PV module under STC using Proteus software

Figure 4(b): P-V characteristic of MSX 60 PV module under STC using Proteus software

2.4 Solar irradiation effect on PV module characteristics.

The current generated by the PV module is proportional to the solar irradiation value. Figure 5 shows the I-V and P-V characteristics of the simulated PV module under a reference temperature of 25 °C and varied irradiation levels. When the solar irradiation is changed, it is noticed that the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) does not change much, but the short-circuit current (I_{sc}) has a significant variation dramatically, increasing or decreasing the generated PV power.

Figure 5(a): I-V characteristics of the simulated PV for different solar irradiation ($T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Figure 5(b): P-V characteristics of the simulated PV for different solar irradiation ($T=25^{\circ}\text{C}$)

2.5 Temperature effect on PV module characteristics

At a constant solar irradiation of 1000 W/m^2 , it is found clearly that there is slight change in the short-circuit current value when the temperature is raised from 25°C to 75°C .

Figure 6(a): I-V characteristics of the simulated PV for different temperature values at constant solar irradiation (1000 W/m^2)

But the open-circuit voltage (VOC) significantly drops, which lowers the amount of power that can be extracted from the PV panel. The I(V) and P(V) characteristics for different temperature values are shown in Figure.6 (a) and Figure.6 (b) respectively

Figure 6(b): P-V characteristics of the simulated PV for different temperature values at constant solar irradiation (1000 W/m^2)

3. SEPIC CONVERTER

Isolated or non-isolated DC-DC converters serve as an intermediate between the PV module and the load to perform the MPPT process. The following classes of non-isolated converters are frequently used: Buck, Boost, Buck-Boost, SEPIC, Cuk, and Zeta. Buck and Boost converters can be described as simple with high efficiency and low order. But they can only increase (Boost) or decrease (Buck) which reduce the range of their applications.

Other converters, such as Buck-Boost and SEPIC, are able to handle loads that are larger or smaller than the optimal load. They can achieve the MPP in spite of changes in the load or weather because to their ability to step up or step down their input voltage. In this paper SEPIC is used, its principal circuit configuration is illustrated in Figure.7. An inductor at the input of the SEPIC converter generates a low ripple continuous input current waveform.

Accurate MPPT performance is easy to attain with this capability. Additionally, the configuration provides isolation between the input and output through capacitor C. Capacitor C_{out}'s protective role is against output short circuits and overloads. Furthermore, in comparison to Buck-Boost and Cuk topologies, the classical SEPIC topology offers the advantage of having identically polarized input and output voltages.

Another notable feature that the SEPIC converter and the Cuk converter have in common is the grounded switch control terminal. However, it should be noted that the output current from the SEPIC converter is irregular, requiring a sizable output capacitor [8].

Figure 7: SEPIC converter

4. MPPT TECHNIQUES

4.1 Perturb and Observe (P&O) Method

P&O method is one of the most popular approaches that is widely used in commercial devices and forms the basis for most of the sophisticated algorithms discussed in specified literature [19].

Figure 8: Flowchart of P&O MPPT method

This method tracks the Maximum Power Point (MPP) by a trial-and-error process. The tracking controller calculates the actual PV power in every iteration by measuring the PV current and voltage. Then, it adjusts the operating voltage in a systematic way while keeping an eye on power fluctuations in order to disturb the operating point. When power increases, the subsequent disturbance stays the same direction; when power decreases, the operating voltage is disturbed in the opposite way. This process is repeated until reaching the MPP. Its flow chart is illustrated by Figure.8.

This approach has the benefit of being universally applicable to all PV modules due to its independence from specialized information about PV properties. However, a number of drawbacks have been stated, and discussed in literature [20]. The tracking speed and perturbation step are the two main factors that determine how effective the tracking algorithm is. Larger steps result in higher oscillations, and fixed perturbation values cause steady-state oscillations proportionate to the step value. There is, however, a trade-off between faster response and steady-state oscillations when smaller steps result in slower response. Furthermore, the perturbation step value lacks genericity, which means that MPPT with a fixed step depends on the system. Variable perturbation stages are used to improve performance. Based on initial challenges and changeable perturbation values

related to output power, these approaches perform better than their fixed perturbation counterparts, even though they are not fully adaptable. Some methods require user-dependent constants for the adaptation of the initial perturbation step and offer true adaptive alterations, but they are computationally demanding because of aggressive derivatives. As a result, step generation value and the controlled variable output from the MPPT block have been used to produce improved P&O approaches [21].

4.2 Incremental Conductance (IncCon) Method

The P&O method exhibit two major limitations as cited in [22]. First, due to the fixed perturbation step size at steady-state operation, oscillations around the MPP persist, leading to inherent power losses. Second, under rapidly changing environmental conditions, the operating point tends to deviate significantly from the true MPP. To address these drawbacks, the Incremental Conductance (IncCon) method was proposed in [22]. Its operational flow chart is given by Figure.9.

Figure 9: Flowchart of conventional IncCon MPPT method

The IncCon is based on the fact that the derivative of (dP/dV) is zero at MPP as shown by equation (5).

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = 0 \quad (5)$$

The development of equation (5) can lead to the following equations:

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = V \frac{dI}{dV} + I \frac{dV}{dV} \quad (6)$$

$$V \frac{dI}{dV} + I = 0 \quad (7)$$

Depending on the instantaneous value of the conductance $\frac{I}{V}$ and its incremental value $\frac{dI}{dV}$, IncCon algorithm can determine the operating point location. It coincides with the MPP if equation (8) is verified. Otherwise, it is to the right side of the MPP if equation (9) is verified or in the left side of MPP in the P-V curve if equation (10) is verified.

$$\frac{dI}{dV} = - \frac{I}{V} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dV} < - \frac{I}{V} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dV} > - \frac{I}{V} \quad (10)$$

4.3 Modified Incremental conductance algorithm

P&O and IncCon algorithms have limitations, such as steady- state oscillations that occur after reaching the MPP. The MPP detection in the IncCon technique is based on the P-V curve's slope.

When the algorithm determines that the working point is at the summit of the P-V curve (slope = zero) and that equation (7) is fulfilled, the duty cycle is kept constant, and its variation is quiescent until the slope changes. However, because of numerical differentiation truncation mistakes, it is uncommon in digital simulations to achieve a zero-slope criterion, as shown in [10], [11].

The sudden increase in solar irradiation can be detected by checking whether the MPP was reached and the increase in both V and I. A permitted error is accepted to stabilize the system around the MPP because the zero will be never obtained. Figure 10 shows the flow chart for the modified algorithm.

The flag 'MPP' initially set to zero is used to indicate whether or not the MPP has been reached. When the MPP is reached, this flag is reset to one, indicating that the condition Equation is satisfied, then the execution of the program is continued.

Figure 10: Flowchart of modified IncCon MPPT method

5 SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 System description and parameters

Figure 11 shows the global structure of the simulated PV system, consisting of a PV module feeding a resistive load connected to a SEPIC converter in addition to MPPT controller. The detail of the PV system using ISIS proteus software is illustrated in Figure.12. The power of the system under study is 120 Wp, therefore two 60W PV modules are connected in series (part a). An Arduino microcontroller (part e) is used to generate the duty cycle driving the MOSFET (part b) based on the acquired values of the voltage and the current of the PV module (parts c and d).

Figure 11: Simulated PV system

The system specifications and parameters are as follow:

$$v_{oc} = 21.1V, v_{mpp} = 17.1V$$

$$i_{sc} = 3.8 \times 2 = 7.6 A, i_{mpp} = 3.5 \times 2 = 7A$$

For continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation of the SEPIC converter, the maximum duty-cycle is calculated by equations (12,13).

$$D = \frac{V_o}{V_{pv} + V_o} \quad (12)$$

$$D_{max} = \frac{V_o}{V_{pvmin} + V_o} \quad (13)$$

Figure 12: Simulated PV systems

5.2 Simulation results for variable solar irradiation

The solar irradiation is increased from 400 W/m² to 1000 W/m² in two steps, then it is decreased to 400 W/m². The system responds accurately and the PV power is increasing from 49W to 120 W.

Figure 13: Solar irradiation profile

Figure 14: Output power for different MPPT algorithms (a): P&O (b): IncCon (C): modified IncCon

When the solar irradiation is decreased (a1, b1 and c1), the system undergoes a transit state before reaching the real MPP value. An overshoot can be observed, its value is lower for the modified IncCon algorithm. The steady states highlighted in a2, b2 and c2 show the superiority of the modified IncCon in term of occurred oscillation. It can be clearly seen the modified IncCon contributes significantly in reducing the steady state oscillation to a minimum value of 0.6W, that means more efficiency.

Figure 15 shows the obtained PV current and voltage for the three algorithms, where the effect of eliminating oscillation in modified IncCon algorithm can be seen clearly.

Figure 15: PV output voltage and current for the studied algorithms

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an improved incremental conductance MPPT is studied and verified using simulation and Arduino implementation. The PV model development and verification is achieved using ISI Proteus software based on single diode model, where the different I-V and P-V curves were generated for STC and for variable solar irradiation and temperature conditions. The SEPIC converter was used for testing the MPPT algorithm on a 120W PV system. The obtained results were very satisfying. The modified IncCon algorithm have contributed to track effectively the MPP in slow as in fast solar irradiation with less overshoot compared to P&O and conventional IncCon techniques. In addition to that, this algorithm has presented no steady state oscillations that contribute strongly in reducing power losses.

The results of this research work contribute substantially in developing more efficient PV systems in less time and at lower cost. Consequently, this will directly improve the quality of life for peoples in urban areas and in isolated places. The obtained results are useful in simulation and for small systems where the rated power is around 120Wp. As perspectives, this work should be followed by an experimental verification allowing the validation of the obtained results as well as the testing of the system for larger scale and under more realistic conditions such as shading, snows or dust.

References

- 1) D. Kweku *et al.*, "Greenhouse Effect: Greenhouse Gases and Their Impact on Global Warming," *J. Sci. Res. Reports*, vol. 17, no. 6, 2018, doi: 10.9734/jsrr/2017/39630.
- 2) M. Kumar, K. P. Panda, J. C. Rosas-Caro, A. Valderrabano-Gonzalez, and G. Panda, "Comprehensive Review of Conventional and Emerging Maximum Power Point Tracking Algorithms for Uniformly and Partially Shaded Solar Photovoltaic Systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 31778–31812, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3262502.
- 3) E. V. S. G. Jhansi Rani, "Control Of PV Integrated DAB Under Shading Conditions Using Improved Incremental Conductance MPPT Scheme," *J. Harbin Eng. Univ.*, vol. 44, no. 11, pp. 644–650, 2023, [Online]. Available: <https://harbinengineeringjournal.com/index.php/journal/article/view/1956/1326>
- 4) O. Boubaker, "MPPT techniques for photovoltaic systems: a systematic review in current trends and recent advances in artificial intelligence," *Discov. Energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s43937-023-00024-2.
- 5) M. L. Katche, A. B. Makokha, S. O. Zachary, and M. S. Adaramola, "A Comprehensive Review of Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) Techniques Used in Solar PV Systems," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 5, 2023. doi: 10.3390/en16052206.
- 6) A. Boudia, S. Messalti, S. Zeghlache, and A. Harrag, "Type-2 fuzzy logic controller-based maximum power point tracking for photovoltaic system," *Electr. Eng. Electromechanics*, no. 1, pp. 16–22, 2025.
- 7) N. Zerzouri, N. B. S. Ali, and N. Benalia, "A maximum power point tracking of a photovoltaic system connected to a three-phase grid using a variable step size perturb and observe algorithm," *Electr. Eng. Electromechanics*, no. 5, pp. 37–46, 2023.
- 8) J. L. Seguel, S. I. Seleme, and L. M. F. Morais, "Comparative Study of Buck-Boost, SEPIC, Cuk and Zeta DC-DC Converters Using Different MPPT Methods for Photovoltaic Applications," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 21, 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15217936.
- 9) H. Bounechba, A. Boussaid, and A. Bouzid, "Experimental validation of fuzzy logic controller based on voltage perturbation algorithm in battery storage photovoltaic system," *Electr. Eng. Electromechanics*, no. 5, pp. 20–27, 2024.
- 10) K. S. Tey and S. Mekhilef, "Modified incremental conductance MPPT algorithm to mitigate inaccurate responses under fast-changing solar irradiation level," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 101, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2014.01.003.
- 11) S. Motahir, A. El Ghzizal, S. Sebti, and A. Derouich, "Modeling of Photovoltaic System with Modified Incremental Conductance Algorithm for Fast Changes of Irradiance," *Int. J. Photoenergy*, vol. 2018, 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/3286479.
- 12) V. Kumar, S. Ghosh, N. K. S. Naidu, S. Kamal, R. K. Saket, and S. K. Nagar, "A current sensor based adaptive step-size MPPT with SEPIC converter for photovoltaic systems," *IET Renew. Power Gener.*, vol. 15, no. 5, 2021, doi: 10.1049/rpg2.12091.

- 13) Z. A. Ghani *et al.*, "Development of a dc to dc buck converter for photovoltaic application utilizing peripheral interface controller," *ARPJ. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 7, 2019.
- 14) H. P. Shaik Munthaz, A. Raghuram, "Comparative Analysis of Cuk, SEPIC, and Cuk-Sepic Fused Converters with Fuzzy MPPT Algorithm for Photovoltaic Systems," *J. Harbin Eng. Univ.*, vol. 45, no. 11, pp. 495–501, 2024.
- 15) T. Sutikno, R. A. Aprilianto, N. R. Nik Idris, and A. S. Samosir, "Performance numerical evaluation of modified single-ended primary-inductor converter for photovoltaic systems," *Int. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 13, no. 4, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v13i4.pp3720-3732.
- 16) H. Abidi, L. Sidhom, and I. Chihi, "Systematic Literature Review and Benchmarking for Photovoltaic MPPT Techniques," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 8. 2023. doi: 10.3390/en16083509.
- 17) A. EL FILALI and M. ZAZI, "Arduino implementation of MPPT with P and O algorithm in photovoltaic systems," *Int. J. Eng. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2021.
- 18) S. Motahhir, A. Chalh, A. El Ghzizal, S. Sebti, and A. Derouich, "Modeling of photovoltaic panel by using proteus," *J. Eng. Sci. Technol. Rev.*, vol. 10, pp. 8–13, 2017.
- 19) N. Gupta *et al.*, "Review on Classical and Emerging Maximum Power Point Tracking Algorithms for Solar Photovoltaic Systems," *J. Renew. Energy Environ.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 18–29, 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.30501/jree.2024.407775.1650>.
- 20) G. Themozhi, K. Srinivasan, T. A. Srinivas, and A. Prabha, "Analysis of suitable converter for the implementation of drive system in solar photovoltaic panels," *Electr. Eng. Electromechanics*, no. 1, pp. 17–22, 2024.
- 21) M. Abdillah, R. C. Batubara, N. I. Pertiwi, and H. Setiadi, "Design of Maximum Power Point Tracking System Based on Single Ended Primary Inductor Converter Using Fuzzy Logic Controller," *Int. J. Intell. Eng. Syst.*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.22266/IJIES2022.0228.32.
- 22) O. Wasynczuk, "Dynamic behavior of a class of photovoltaic power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Appar. Syst.*, vol. PAS-102, no. 9, 1983, doi: 10.1109/TPAS.1983.318109.